

gions of the reservoir area. The salt reclamation process indeed had a direct impact on rice productivity, net farm income, and employment generation. The indirect benefits were an increase in

land value and conservation of the soil-crop environment.

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Exposure of Bangladeshi rice farmers to early flood risk

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Floodplain agriculture in Bangladesh is characterized by smallholders operating marginal parcels of land, with heavy reliance on the winter rice crop. When the annual floods, which normally begin in early or mid-June, arrive even a week or two early, they may submerge the standing rice crop prior to harvest, often causing considerable damage. Where overbank flooding from main river channels is the principal source of early flood risk, as in the case with flash floods in the northeast, structural means of flood control such as submersible embankments may be effectively employed. In north-central Bangladesh, however, much of the early flooding is from local rainfall impoundment, and therefore structural methods are less helpful. Using biophysical and socioeconomic data collected in north-central Bangladesh, we investigated (1) the extent and patterns of damage caused by 1- and 2-wk early floods and (2) what readily available (nonstructural) opportunities existed to reduce such risk.

A previous floodplain livelihood project (Barr 2000) in the Charan *beel* (floodplain water body) and floodplain area in Tangail District had collected a set of biophysical and socioeconomic

data over the 1997-98 hydrological year. These included flood depth and spread measurements, plot-level cropping pattern, monthly crop growth stage, and socioeconomic information. These data were stored in a project geographic information system (GIS). The start of the flood in 1997-98 was perceived in the study area as normal. On that basis, we took these data as the baseline, simulated the arrival of 1- and 2-wk early flood events using GIS methods, computed damage estimates using simple water depth and yield damage parameters to answer question 1, and queried the plot-specific cropping pattern information to answer question 2 above.

Results revealed that, as expected, plot-level damage due to early floods was strongly dictated by elevation of the land. Following the standard definition of land elevation in Bangladesh, 45% of the very low (VL) plots were seen from the simulations to suffer some damage even from a 1-wk early flood. Significantly, when the damage does occur, it is likely to be substantial. Most of the affected VL plots are almost completely damaged by a 1-wk early flood. Two-week early flood damaged about half the VL plots. For the low (L) plots, 1-wk early

floods damaged only 8% of the plots, while 2-wk early floods damaged about 40% of the plots. Higher land elevations were not seen to suffer any damage from these simulated flood events.

It is not surprising that VL plots suffer most from early flood events. But what factors explain the damage to some VL plots, while others remain undamaged? Analysis of plot-level cropping patterns provided an interesting clue in this regard. Every single undamaged VL plot was found to be devoted to a single crop of winter rice, whereas 90% of the damaged VL plots were found to include a mustard crop just prior to the winter rice. Mustard is a cash crop, and the farmers in the area use proceeds from its sale to finance expensive inputs for the high-yielding rice crop (HYV) immediately following. The necessity for some farmers to do this appears to be delaying the planting of rice, resulting in correspondingly later harvests and increased exposure to early floods. Another interesting pattern found in the data was that the damaged VL plots were mostly planted to the older generation of relatively long-duration HYVs such as IR8, while shorter duration varieties with comparable yield, such as BR26 and BR28,

have been available for some time now.

In summary, our results show that even the slightly early flood events (1 to 2 wk) that occur with reasonable frequency in north-central Bangladesh are prone to cause significant damage to very low elevation winter rice plots. Yet, our evidence shows that this is not a problem requiring new investments in technology. Rather, credit provision for input financing and

extension help with existent shorter duration varieties can go a long way in ameliorating this situation.

Reference

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